

EBC-IX
2025

EDITED BY

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ISBN 978-618-5558-13-0

9th European **Bioremediation** Conference

e-Book of Abstracts

ORGANIZED BY

TECHNICAL
UNIVERSITY
OF CRETE

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA

SUPPORTED BY

Περιφέρεια Κρήτης
Region of Crete

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Chania, Crete, Greece
15-19 June 2025

Adsorptive removal of Contaminants of Emerging Concern from Urban Wastewater using Bivalve Shells

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ABSTRACT

Bivalve shells have been identified as a potential material for removing contaminants from wastewater, as a refining step, advancing in water purification and aligning with the UN's Clean Water and Sanitation goal. However, research to date has been limited to bench-scale experiments. This study aims to compare the efficiency of different shell types in removing contaminants of emerging concern (CEC) from a tertiary effluent originated from an urban wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), using a fixed-bed column adsorption approach in a large-scale experimental setup. Three shell types were tested: *Corbicula fluminea* milled shells (1-5 mm), *C. fluminea* calcined shells (700 °C, 2h; 1-25 mm) and a mixture of clam, oyster, and cockle shells, 1:1:1 volume, 1-5 mm). Pre-treated wastewater from a METland® system installed at the WWTP was collected and used to simultaneously feed three 2L vertical columns, each packed with a shell type, under a flow rate of 4 L·day⁻¹. Three temporal replicates were obtained for each treatment.

The use of bivalve shells resulted in a significant increase in pH from 6.3 (± 0.5) to 7.7 (± 0.5), as well as in inorganic carbon (IC) concentrations, which rose from 3.5 (± 3) mg·L⁻¹ to 10.1 (± 3) mg·L⁻¹ with clam shells, to 6.6 (± 2) mg·L⁻¹ with calcined clam shells, and to 14.0 (± 4) mg·L⁻¹ with the shell mixture (mean ± SD). The removal of the four most abundant CEC was pronounced after seven days of operation (Figure 1). Removal efficiencies followed the trend: calcined clam shells (74%) > clam shells (70%) > shell mixture (66%). These findings suggest that bivalve shells have significant potential for wastewater refinement in WWTPs. Untreated clam shells and shell mixtures may be more economically viable due to lower processing costs which, allied to the minor differences in the toxicity abatement among shell types, suggests that untreated clam shells and shell mixtures might be suitable for wastewater refinement.

Figure 1: Contaminant concentrations measured at the column inlet and after passage through each column following a 7-day operational period. Data are presented as mean values with standard deviation, based on the average of three experiments.

Acknowledgements: The financial support by FCT/MCTES to UID Centro de Estudos do Ambiente e Mar (CESAM) + LA/P/0094/2020 through national funds is acknowledged. S.B-H gratefully acknowledges the Regional Government of Madrid for supporting this research through the Ph.D. fellowship program (IND2023/AMB-28918). This work was supported by project NYMPHE, funded by the European Union through the Grant 101060625 (doi: 10.3030/101060625) - views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EU or the European Research Executive Agency; neither the EU or the granting authority can be held for them.

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Overview

- Wastewater may contain a wide variety of contaminants.
- Bivalve shells can remove contaminants from wastewater, as a refining step.
- *Corbicula fluminea* is an invasive clam species found worldwide.
- Their shells can be used to remove contaminants from the water (e.g., metals) but the efficiency to remove pharmaceuticals is scarcely known.

AIM to compare the efficiency of different shell types in removing contaminants of emerging concern (CEC) from a tertiary effluent originated from an urban wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), using a fixed-bed column adsorption approach in a large-scale experimental setup.

Methodology

shells collection

dH₂O washing | drying at 60 °C

* samples > chemical and ecotoxicological assessment

raw WW

Results

Shells resulted in a significant increase in pH from 6.3 (± 0.5) to 7.7 (± 0.5), as well as in inorganic carbon (IC) concentrations.

Removal of the 4 most abundant contaminants was pronounced after 7 days of operation. In average (considering all shell types), the removal was 81 % for paraxanthine, 72% for caffeine, 67% for valsartan, and 61 % for naproxen.

Removal efficiencies followed the trend: calcined clam shells (74%) > clam shells (70%) > shell mixture (66%).

Ecotoxicological evaluation (day 7)

Shells had a low effect in toxicity abatement considering responses by *Aliivibrio fischeri*, *Daphnia magna*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus* and *Lactuca sativa*.

Differences in efficacy for toxicity abatement among shell types were minor, yet significant for *Lactuca sativa* root growth.

Conclusions

Bivalve shells have potential for wastewater refinement in WWTPs.

Untreated clam shells and shell mixtures may be more economically sustainable for wastewater treatment refining due to lower processing costs plus the mild differences found in toxicity abatement promoted by different shell types.

This approach supports circular economy and exhibits ecological and environmental benefits on aquatic systems.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

FCT/MCTES to UID CESAM + LA/P/0094/2020

Project NYMPHE

EU Grant 101060625, doi: 10.3030/101060625

Regional Government of Madrid for supporting the Ph.D. fellowship program (IND2023/AMB-28918)